

DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC AND CREATIVE ABILITIES IN CHILDREN

Egamberdiyeva Irodaxon

The teacher of the Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abdumajidova Mohlaroyim Nozimjon

Student of the 304th group of the Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10315621>

Abstract: In this article, the main goal of preschool education is to prepare children for school studies, to form them into healthy, well-developed independent individuals, about the formation of scientific and creative activities in children, Children learn through creative activities it is said that they can develop their creative abilities by creating and learning new things, making a profit for themselves.

Key words: education, independence, training, creative ability, development, independent person, education, goal.

The reforms implemented in the field of education in our republic during the years of independence and the opportunities created in this regard have expanded tremendously and today they are becoming one of the important priorities of our state policy. In particular, the current development of the field of preschool education, which is considered the first link of continuous education, is a clear proof of this. The main goal of pre-school education is to prepare children for studying at school, to make them healthy, well-developed independent individuals, and to bring up a well-rounded person educated in the spirit of national and universal values. Therefore, preschool education is one of the most important periods of a child's life. Different factors influence children's scientific outlook in different ways. Among these factors, the development of creative and logical thinking is the most important. After all, the process of formation of imagination and concepts in a child starts from the preschool educational institution, and this period is the most important stage in terms of the content of the formation of the worldview. That is why the period of preschool age is the main period in the formation of concepts and ideas.

Developing scientific and creative abilities in children is a very important topic. As we know, in preschool educational organizations, various activities are organized to develop children's creativity, and children are directed to creative thinking. Based on this knowledge, preschoolers should have the following skills.

After completing the educational activity in the field of "creativity", a 6-7-year-old child:

- shows interest in art and culture;
- values national traditions and perceives them as a part of everyday life;
- independently expresses a preference for a certain type of art;
- uses acquired knowledge and skills to create and implement creative plans in various life situations;
- understands the role of human creativity in changing the world.

A child's creativity can be developed not only in special classes, but for the development of children's imagination, play, which is the main activity of preschool children, is also of great importance. The best way to develop creative skills is through play. It is in the game that the child takes the first steps of creative activity. Adults should not only watch the children's game, but also manage its development, enrich it, and introduce creative elements into the game. In addition, there are special games that can be played with children in their free time

to develop creative skills. Children can develop their creative skills by creating and learning new things, benefiting themselves through creative activities. They create new insights and approaches by sharing their experiences, knowledge and ideas with others. Don't forget that spiritual development will be enhanced in an environment that encourages learning and mastering them. Also, with the importance of shifting responsibilities and coordination, rejecting and teaching children through new teaching methods increases their local level of thinking, discussing, questioning and reinforcing and expressing their opinions. In addition, there are many experiences in developing children's scientific and creative activities. These, in turn, are divided into 6 stages:

1. Experiments and learning: However, experiments provide opportunities for children to experience and learn. They help their personal development by facilitating the level of creation by being engaged in equipping, shaping, putting colors and shapes. These types of activities are important in improving education and creativity in children.
2. Questioning and discussion: Discussion, debate and questioning are very important for children to develop logical concepts. Providing them with news, reading, finding information, and opportunities to answer questions and form opinions will help them develop their life skills.
3. Engage in creative communication: Children should be given opportunities to fulfill their creative imagination, imagine, think and think of new things. For them, it is possible to develop their creative abilities through toys, creations and creative activities.
4. Quality scientific information: It is very important to provide children with access to quality, scientific information. Providing them with readings in their favorite fields, and providing them with scientific information about interests and news in the natural sciences, mathematics, technology or creative fields, will help them develop their scientific skills.
5. Coordinated educational tools: Technologies and educational tools should be provided well, giving children a chance to learn how to find answers to their own questions.
6. Deadlines: It is important to set deadlines and goals for children. It gives them motivation, helps to increase their patience and decision making skills.

Based on these facts, it can be more convenient and effective to use the development of scientific and creative abilities in children. It is also important to engage them in advanced learning, to keep up with the changes in the most important learning environment for their change and development.

References:

1. Toshtemirova S. A. (2020). Quality of education and its democratization as a scientific problem // Continuous education
2. Epiphany D.B. Psychology of creativity. Textbook. Benefit. - M.: Academy, 2002.-
3. Levin, V.A. Cultivating creativity. - Tomsk: Peleng, 1992